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Department of English Applied Linguistics***Abstract**

The purpose of this article to bring into discussion the features of Noun Phrases in Japanese since definiteness is ultimately influenced by the morphosyntactic and morphologic phenomenology at a deep level. As we know, features are generally of three categories, privative, binary and attributive, with the latter containing more than one feature. Here we will resort only to emphasize a few characteristics of the system. Features have gained increasing importance within theories of syntax and morphology in Japanese. This was obtained in two different manners. As theories try to capture ever more subtle distinctions, the features involved become more fine-grained and the noun phrases allow for more possible combinations.

Keywords: Determiners Japanese, Particles, Lexicality, Topic Definiteness, Ono, Shibatani.

4. The Features System of Noun Phrases in Japanese

In this chapter we will analyze the structure and features of the NP which is remarkable in that it shows a large cross linguistic variation, since these characteristics contribute to the rendition of definiteness as a valid concept for both English and Japanese. As a matter of fact, the widespread and complex multiple faceted body of theories allows us to draw important conclusions with regard to the interpretation of definiteness with semantic and morphosyntactic arguments. This chapter aims to describe definiteness by taking into consideration the features and structure of the lower noun phrase. The semantics, morphology, syntax and phonology interact with each other by means of a featural system in order to turn the process of definiteness into a syntactically driven phenomenon that acts on its own.

This section is a summarized investigation into the behaviour of the features that exist, at least in Japanese, in the lower branches of the nominal projection, namely at the lexical level. The term feature is employed along the chapter to encode a minimal distinction between linguistic units that individually represent a certain relevant property for definiteness. For example, if we look closer at privative features, we can imagine words share the same linguistic behaviour with exception for one property that cannot be further divided and which becomes eloquent.

Definite or indefinite features are structured in a two-fold classification: (i) what is the internal structure of a feature and (ii) how can larger structures can be obtained by adjoining features? Our purposal in this section is to assume that definiteness is syntactically determined at a deeper level and a bundle of features represent the tractioning wheels behind the linguistic mechanism. We evidently only resume discussing what we can achieve as simplest possible in this thesis (with privative and binary features) without deepening the discussion further with increased complexity (e.g. Lexical Functional Grammar), evaluating them on the ground of the already discussed system of Borer's minimalist program.

4.1. Features in Japanese

Features in Japanese have been primarily described by Unoue (1978) who tried to borrow early transformational rules that applied directly to English morphemes

(such as those proposed by Postal (1966) to capture determiner-noun agreement) and frame them on the peculiarities of Japanese. According to him, a NP starts out as in Unoue (1978:49)

1. [NP[Bareun]]

[Noun[Stem^a-
lumn]][PARTICLE][Nominative/Dative]]

The above structure arises as a result of Japanese not having overt means for Gender and Number expressions. Nonetheless, particles are employed to modify a noun. For example, an obligatory transformational rule applies to mark the nominal suffix *-er* to the determiner in (2) and (3) when nominalization occurs in these structure:

2. Hon o yomu shigoto no hito.

N. book Part. Acc. Vb. Read N. work Part. Nom N. person

A person whose activity is to read. (a student)

3. Ryori o suru shigoto no onna.

N. meal Part. Acc. Vb. do N. work Part. Nom N. person

A woman whose activity is to cook. (housewife)

This nominalizing process is highly characteristic to Japanese and it compensates for the lack of Gender and Number markers that English exhibits. Unoue (1978:54) then offers the following structure in order to argue for the syntactic grammaticality of the aforementioned examples:

4.

[NP[Determiner^{un}[PART.[ACCUSATIVE]]][Verb[Stem^alumn][Noun[PART.[NOMINATIVE] HEAD Noun]]]]

Following Chomsky (1965), who made a number of transformational rules more abstract, replacing the morphemes with abstract featural content, Shibuya (1982) proposes another system of features for Japanese in which he describes the categories of Number and Gender along with Case as intrinsic features of Noun Phrases in Japanese. For this fact, nouns *'present both Gender and Number co-indexed in the syntactic structure of a Noun by means of paratactic mapping'* (Shibuya, 1982:31):

5. Shakai de takusan no tenin ga taisetsu na koto o hanashimashita

N. *conference* Part. *DAT*. N. *Gathering* Part. *NOM*.
N. *Clerk* Part. *TOP* Adj. *Important* N. *Thing* Part.

Many clerks tackled with important issues at the conference.

Onna mo otoko mo arimashita.

N. *women* Part. N. *men* Part. Vb. PAST *b*

There were both women and men. Shibuya 1982:58

According to the author, even though in (95) there are no overt grammatical items for Gender and Number marking or to express definiteness, the paratactic mapping introduced by Shibuya as a specialized process in Japanese helps drawing closer the grammatical specificity of Japanese to the English paradigm. In other

6.

From this point, features have gained increasing importance within theories of syntax and morphology in Japanese. This was obtained in two different manners. As theories try to capture ever more subtle distinctions, the features involved become more fine-grained. For example, some authors like Tokutsuba (1988) argue that features in Japanese must also be derived based on semantic grounds since *the vast majority of language begins with perception* (p.91).

His theory includes the analysis of so-called organisational elements in Japanese grammar by means of a semantic system of features (e.g. *cat* should not be described as [+animate] [-human] as in English, but rather *four legged vertebrate which meows*), the taxonomic reinforcement of clauses (semantic elements impose the structure of a clause and its properties), the proposal for a larger domain of features in Japanese etc. According to him, the left periphery of the clause *becomes ever more decomposed due to the different features and functional projections* which Tokutsuba (1988:14) demonstrates can act independently of each other:

7. Sensei wa heya ni doubutsu o irete wa ikenai to iimashita.

N. *teacher* Part. *Nom* N. *room* Part. *Dat*. N. *animal* Part. *Acc*. Vb. *Enter* Part. *Nom*. Vb. *Neg* *come* Vb. Teacher said that animals are not allowed in the room.

While the traditional English analysis of features in the previous example would usually assign binary characteristics to nouns, Tokutsuba's (1988:17) analysis proposes a larger array of properties that must be brought into discussion:

8. Sensei: [+animate] [+human] [teacher] [Japanese] [University]

Doubutsu: [+animate] [-human] [dog] [cat] [hamster] [parrot]

Heya: [-animate] [+concrete] [+utility] [Education] [University]

Tokutsuba takes into account the order of words in Japanese as a linguistic token which also assigns features to nouns and even verbs. He coins the notion of

words, both Gender and Number are overtly emphasized in Japanese through:

- Pluralizing nominalization: *taksuan no tenin* (many clerks)

- Contextual Indexation of Gender: *onna mo otoko mo* (both women and men)

- Number Referential Mapping: *onna mo otoko mo* (plural nouns from *takusan*)

Shibuya (1982) pleads for a more comprehensive feature system in Japanese Noun Phrases, since he argued for the syntactic relevance of Gender and Number against Yamada (1978), while, at the same time, discovering novel means of expression for these categories in Japanese:

scope visibility. It draws a hierarchy within the structure of the clause, meaning that, based on word order, lexemes have a greater wield on scope between each other judging the place they occupy in a sentence (with 0 being the highest scope of a noun). Even implied nouns receive scope like *sensei* in (9) (Tokutsuba, 1988:18)

9. Sensei: [Scope: 0] [+authority]

Doubutsu: [Scope: 2] [+argument]

4.1.1. *Conclusions of This Section*

In order to comprehend the interpretation of definiteness in Japanese it is highly important to analyze the structure of features for Japanese because, as pointed out before, most authors agree that nouns in Japanese are inherently definite. While it is a bold statement, we cannot fully agree with such an idea, mostly because NPs lack Number or Gender and articles, so the problem of definiteness cannot be solved by simply claiming the argument of null-NPs as sufficient and satisfactory. For this reason, I provided the analysis of Tokutsuba (1988) who endeavors to part ways with the tradition formalist analysis and bring into discussion semantic content in order to characterize Japanese nouns.

The thorough account for the lack of Gender and Number on Japanese nouns and the conservation, at the same time, of the possibility of expressing definiteness, led us to show that this problem was tackled before in a professional manner by Shibuya (1982), who emphasizes three methods for the formation of Number and Gender in Japanese, namely by pluralizing nominalization (*takusan no tenin* - many clerks), contextual indexation of Gender (*onna mo otoko mo* - both women and men), and number referential mapping (*onna mo otoko mo* - plurality of nouns derived from the adverb *takusan*) even though there are no overt grammatical items for Gender and Number marking or to express definiteness, the paratactic mapping introduced by Shibuya as a specialized process in Japanese helps drawing closer the grammatical specificity of Japanese regarding definiteness.

However, the above mechanism was not sufficient, so I decided to bring into discussion the semantic analysis of features which depart from the English tradition by bringing into discussion environmental content, pragmatic and empirical features. For this reason, it is fairly acceptable to conclude that nouns in Japanese are as complex as their English counterpart and allow for the expression of definiteness in a manner different from its counterparts in Europe, but not exclusive. I emphasized that, even though some linguists agree that Japanese NPs are inherently definite, this is not always the case, since some nouns are analyzed as [+animate] like in *sensei* (teacher), while others are analyzed as [-animate] like in *heya* (room), meaning that a simple formalist analysis would simply render obsolete our efforts to understand definiteness in Japanese by claiming that all nouns are inherently definite, even though there

is no Number or Gender and such state of things would suggest against this statement.

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